

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Teaching children to action in the process of physical education is carried out under the direct guidance of the educator, as well as in the independent activity of children under his supervision. When teaching movement activities, the child develops consciousness, willpower and emotional forces, as well as his practical skills of movement are formed. Teaching the child's inner world to history, thinking, gradually forming worldview, moral qualities; the action performed by children, beneficial for health and overall physical development, affects the activity in a purposeful manner. In accordance with the content of education, preschool children constitute selected physical exercises, moving games on the basis of state requirements for education. In the

ABSTRACT

This article provides a scientific overview of the physical education of preschool children, combining it with physical education from an early age, which is the basis for healthy and energetic growth of children. In this article the process of preschool education, the ways of proper organization of physical education in children and the principles used in the training are described.

process of Education, adults give children the experience of purposeful activity. Its content also includes the experience of mastering movements that serve for development and improvement. When working with preschool children, it is very necessary to take into account their age characteristics, some knowledge that the child will benefit from in the activity of conscious movement; the unit of knowledge about the methods of activity, activities and qualifications and skills of their implementation, which will teach the child to movements, constitute components due to the working processes. One of the parts is the experience of creative activity. A person who has not been taught to think independently since childhood and has mastered everything

after it has been prepared can not show him the qualities that are given to him by nature. Therefore, society can not stand completely indifferent to the study of the younger generation in creative activity. In the process of educating the activity of the movement, adults (parents, educators) take into account the psychophysiological features of the development of children, put before them new functions of movement. The fact that the child is increasingly able to solve new movement tasks in the process of exercise, and in connection with this, the great opportunities that arise change the nature and quality of movements. Something that is very characteristic for this age period is a becoming new quality of reindeer in the process of teaching new exercises. Chunchi, the child's gait is completely different at the first moment and at the end of the second year. This phenomenon can be cited as the old thing of innovation as a diactic inkor, an obyektiv condition of all development and conflict resolution, a moving factor. Development in each area can not pass without denying the forms of living before it. Such a complex development process is constantly shrinking in the interaction of external and internal conditions. Overcoming difficulties and solving new tasks will create a positive emotional mood in the child. This achieved goal occurs due to new muscle sensations, according to the trainer's assessment. Strengthening the resulting changes will serve as a wake-up to the pursuit of higher achievements. This complex process should always be under the supervision of a tutor. On the one hand, it is necessary to ensure that the child understands the function of a new movement, on the other hand, it is necessary to instill in the child the

independence and enthusiasm to implement it on the basis of existing real action opportunities, as well as emerging interest, emotions. Education requires the child to concentrate attention on one place, to develop an active imagination, active thinking, memory: for example, if the educational process is of interest and is in an emotional spirit – emotional; if the pattern of action is shown figuratively by the educator and is performed by children – figurative; if the consistency of the action of the game and the performance of all the elements of the exercise in their independent execution is understood and remembered by the tasks, if the verbal reasoning is connected with the practical performance of the exercise by the children themselves – the motor movement. For this, training should be free, so that the exercises can be performed consciously, independently. Moral education in the education of children is a direct link with the formation of the spiritual sense and consciousness of the child, the development of his moral qualities, such as nobility and mutual assistance, aspiration to the goal, honesty, justice. The whole process of teaching the right actions educates aesthetic perception in children. Beautiful actions that children gradually master, clear purification, creative expression of Game images characteristic of their age, poetic texts in games, the beginning of the game, counting – all this serves the task of educating aesthetic taste in children. Of great importance is the external decoration of children's and educators' costumes, physical education manuals, etc. The organization of the educational process allows children to train in the labor movements they are able to achieve. It is necessary for the educator

to ensure that children keep the equipment of physical education themselves tidy and clean (compact wrapped flags, ironed tape, handkerchiefs, etc.).k.) regularly stands as required. About this in the first place caregivers on duty and place the necessary items on the available. At the same time, they also pay attention to the layout of the subject and inventory, so that all children are comfortable to use. Children wash balls, balls, etc. from time to time, wiping large appliances. In such an event, all educators take part in the leadership of the educator. Thus, in the process of teaching actions, mental abilities, moral and aesthetic feelings develop in children, a conscious attitude to their activities and, in connection with this, aspiration to the goal, organization is formed. All this is the implementation of a general approach to the educational process in interdependence. This process contributes to the formation of a comprehensively developed personality.

Methods of conducting physical education classes in preparatory groups (5-6 years)

In the process of conducting and substantiating physical education classes, the following didactic principles are used: systematicity and consistency; consciousness, independence and creative activity; optimal inclusion of visual, verbal and practical methods of education; the basis of comprehension and individual performance; the unity of frontal, group and individual forms of education, the principle of increasing the requirements. They are very important conditions of pedagogy and represent the methodological laws of the single pedagogical process of education and training in itself.

The principle of systematization and consistency is mandatory for all complexes of activities (regime, tempering, formation of movement skills), which are used for the purposes of physical education. Systematism is an expression of the exact consistency of physical education classes on the basis of continuity, regularity, planning of the process of physical education during the entire pre-school period, the obligatory alternation of loading and rest, the consistency, sequence of classes, the interaction of content. Systematism is manifested by the interaction and interdependence of knowledge, skills and abilities: for example, the assimilation of children's material (a given task) allows them to rely on it and move on the assimilation of new material, and the new material, in turn, prepares children to know the latter. Children who are brought up every day at a certain time, according to their character, perform various physical exercises (morning Gymnastics, physical education classes, movement activities during a walk, etc.).k.) systematic performance as well as conditioning activities will teach children to the prescribed recovery-upbringing regime. When systematic training is interrupted, a decrease in the level of functional capacity achieved during breaks between them, and sometimes a regression of morphological indicators is observed. This active muscle tissue is manifested in a decrease in its comparative weight, changes in its structural components and other negative manifestations. Physical education requires a repetition of the skills of the movement that is being formed. Only dynamic stereotypes of movement are formed, as they are repeated many times. For effective repetition, such a system is

necessary, in which the mastered movement is connected with a new one, in other words, the process of repetition acquires the character of variability (change of exercises, the condition of performance, the variety of techniques, the difference in form and content of training in general). In addition, repetition provides long-term re-adaptation in the field of morphology and functionality. On the basis of them, physical attributes develop (A.N. Krestovnikov). The introduction of new stimulants to the generated dynamic stereotypes takes place without drastic changes in the conditions under which the slowness is observed. I.P. Pavlov stressed that slow pace and exercise in pedagogy were the main physiological rule.

Conclusion Teaching methods involve the integration of a system of methods in relation to the learning process, taking into account specific didactic issues, real tools and conditions of teaching. The most important of these methods in the process of physical training is "the method of coordination of physical stress and the order of combining these stresses with rest." The child's nervous system is extremely flexible and highly susceptible to external influences. Therefore, alternating movements with rest determines the optimal dynamics of the body, ensures the timely recovery process and increases the ability to work.

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